

Empirical Analysis of Federated Learning Algorithms: A Federated Research Infrastructure Use Case

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Abstract

Research Infrastructures offer resources and services to extensive communities of researchers, enabling them to perform experiments and promote innovation. Additionally, these infrastructures can be utilized beyond the realm of research, such as in education or public service. The SLICES consortium is tasked with delivering a fully programmable, distributed, virtualized, and remotely accessible federated research infrastructure across Europe, which includes advanced computing, storage, and networking capabilities, along with interconnection through dedicated high-speed links. This initiative will facilitate extensive, experimental research across a range of scientific fields. The processing of data, particularly in the realm of Machine Learning, holds significant appeal for the prospective audience of SLICES. Based on these considerations, this study seeks to leverage this unique Research Infrastructure along with its Cloud-based development and deployment capabilities to explore Federated Learning (FL) methodologies. Specifically, we assess the efficacy of two FL aggregation algorithms, namely FedAvg and FedProx, in environments characterized by both system and statistical heterogeneity, which are likely to be realistic and common scenarios in future community-focused, shared Research Infrastructures, such as those previously mentioned. Our findings indicate that the FedProx algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to the FedAvg algorithm in these contexts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Federated Learning constitutes a core paradigm within Deep Learning models and serves as a distinctive deployment model across Research Infrastructures. The Scientific Large Scale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies consortium, often referred to as SLICES, aims to furnish research communities with a comprehensive environment for conducting experiments and promoting innovation. This environment is fully programmable, virtualized, distributed, and accessible remotely, offering advanced computing, storage, and networking capabilities. It includes inter-site connectivity facilitated by dedicated high-speed links, which are established through consortium-level agreements with GÉANT, a collaboration among European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs). Through GÉANT, NRENs collectively provide an information ecosystem of infrastructure and services designed to enhance research, education, and innovation on a global scale.

SLICES seeks to establish a unified research infrastructure that integrates various technologies and services while accommodating geographically dispersed research objectives. (SLICES-RI, 2021b).

The field of Machine Learning is expanding rapidly and is becoming increasingly vital as a growing number of researchers and industries embrace it. Federated Learning represents an innovative method for training models in close proximity to individual user data (Li et al., 2019). Federated Learning improves conventional machine learning methods by incorporating a built-in feature that safeguards training data regarding privacy. This approach has been adopted by various established technology companies, such as Google, the originator of federated learning (Dhada et al., 2020), and Apple, a major rival in the industry with its virtual assistant technology.

Figure 1 illustrates the potential functioning of Federated Learning (FL) as a conventional collaboration model for analogous research endeavors, which can be conducted remotely without the necessity of sharing sensitive data, utilizing the research infrastructure. In this diagram, the uppermost layer represents Federated Learning, which consists of users distributed across various geographical locations at the lower layer, connected through a network backbone that serves as the middle layer.

The research activities conducted in geographically isolated regions for particular objectives can be integrated, and the performance (e.g., training) or accuracy (e.g., inference) attained may be enhanced through the support of Federated Learning techniques within a research framework.

As federated learning (FL) applications continue to grow, they are entering the Healthcare sector by safeguarding patient’s medical information, thereby ensuring confidentiality (Gope et al., 2021). Additionally, they are being utilized in the Insurance industry to assess the risks associated with clients (Gupta et al., 2022), and for instance, in predicting keyboard input (Hard et al., 2018). This evolution signifies a rapidly expanding field of

Figure 1: Federated Learning Comprised Research Infrastructure.

research. A research infrastructure that provides federated learning as a service to prospective users creates a cohesive framework for researchers, allowing them to benefit from enhanced data privacy, improved performance, and minimized communication overhead.

Counterbalancing its inherent capabilities, Federated Learning (FL) faces the challenge of heterogeneity regarding both the devices (system heterogeneity) and the data (statistical heterogeneity). Specifically, concerning the former, FL typically involves nodes with varying computational and/or storage capacities to take part in the training process (De Vita and Bruneo, 2020). Also, the distribution of such private data among all the participating clients can be Independent and Identically Distributed (IID) or Non-Independent and Identically Distributed (NIID) (Long et al. 2021). Figure 2 provides an example of data distribution in IID and NIID environments. It can be noted that in IID data, the datasets of the two clients exhibit similarities, whereas in NIID data, the clients possess distinct data classes. The presence of NIID data leads to the challenge of statistical heterogeneity (Li et al., 2018).

In an effort to address heterogeneity and reduce high communication costs, differential privacy (Wei et al., 2020) for security, along with optimization techniques that facilitate local updates and minimal participation, have become a favored strategy for federated learning (Gad, 2020). Specifically, FedAvg (McMahan et al., 2017) is an iterative approach that has established itself as the standard optimization method in federated environments.

The FedAvg algorithm executes a fixed number of E epochs of Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) across K devices, where E is a small constant and K represents a minor portion of the total devices within the network. In situations where stragglers are present, meaning devices that operate at a slower pace, the FedAvg algorithm excludes them if they cannot complete

Figure 2: Distribution of Data in IID and NIID Environment.

E local epochs within the specified timeframe. Conversely, when faced with dissimilar (heterogeneous) local objectives F_k , an excessive number of local epochs may steer each device towards the optimal solution of its local objective rather than the global objective, which could result in the method diverging and consequently lacking convergence guarantees to define its behavior.

It has been observed that the presence of such heterogeneity leads to a decline in the performance of Federated Learning (FL) when utilizing the FedAVG algorithm. To mitigate the impact of both system and statistical heterogeneity within the FL framework, researchers have introduced the FedProx algorithm (Li et al., 2018) which serves as an enhanced version of the FedAvg algorithm, equipped with the added capability to manage stragglers and Non-IID data.

As FedAvg excludes devices that execute partial model updates, meaning those that cannot complete a fixed number of E epochs, it solely takes into account the devices that successfully perform the full E epochs. In contrast, FedProx does not eliminate these slower devices, rather, it accepts partial model updates from them as well.

Furthermore, to mitigate the effects of differing local updates, a proximal term is incorporated into the local sub-problem. Specifically, rather than solely minimizing the local function $F_k(\cdot)$, device k employs its preferred local solver to approximately minimize the subsequent objective h_k :

$$\min_w h_k(w; w^t) = F_k(w) + \frac{\mu}{2} \|w - w^t\|^2 \quad (1)$$

where $\frac{\mu}{2} \|w - w^t\|^2$ is the proximal term while w and w^t are weight associated with local and global model respectively. μ is a hyperparameter that controls the strength of the proximal term.

Incorporating a proximal term into the objective enhances the stability of the method and increases the overall accuracy of federated learning within heterogeneous networks, leading to a notable improvement in the average absolute testing accuracy in highly heterogeneous environments.

Consequently, this study concentrates on assessing the effectiveness of the FL algorithms, specifically FedAvg and FedProx, across various heterogeneous environments utilizing different datasets and models. Our empirical findings indicate that FedProx outperforms FedAvg when dealing with NIID data. This conclusion is drawn from the utilization of the SLICES Research Infrastructure, which offers valuable insights into how it can assist users in organizing and planning their experiments.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II gives us an overview of the current literature about FL, Section III describes the methodology and simulation, Section IV presents the results and their analysis, and, at last, Section V outlines our conclusions and planned future scope of the work.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Federated Learning (FL) refers to a machine learning framework where the user’s sensitive data remains on their device, allowing for the training of a local model. Unlike traditional methods of training deep learning models, which involve pooling user data at a centralized location, as illustrated in Figure 3, the central server’s role in federated learning is to compile the training conducted on the individual devices using their local data. In FL, model updates are transmitted in rounds, with each device employing a local training method such as Stochastic Gradient Descent, subsequently sending the (current, locally-trained) model back to the server. The server then consolidates these models. The updated model can be redistributed thereafter. Figure 3 represents the process flow in FL architecture.

Federated learning offers clear benefits regarding privacy. It addresses the data privacy issues associated with earlier machine learning systems by enabling data to remain decentralized, thereby complicating the process for attackers to obtain information from individual users. This occurs because the data remains on the devices, compelling attackers to bypass device security instead of attempting to steal data, which is more susceptible during transmission (Nishio and Yonetani, 2019). Despite this advantage, there are numerous difficulties and opportunities for advancement in federated learning, which we discuss further in later sections.

In (Li et al., 2018), the authors have introduced the FedProx algorithm, which incorporates a proximal term into the FedAvg algorithm to address

Figure 3: Federated Learning Architecture.

both statistical and system heterogeneity. Statistical heterogeneity poses a significant challenge in federated learning, as it has been noted that the algorithm’s performance varies considerably when the data distribution across the participating devices is non-IID. When the data points from individual devices deviate from their original source, the effectiveness of federated learning diminishes slightly, leading to an increase in model complexity.

Li et al. (Pan and Yang, 2010) discuss various approaches for training in diverse environments, including local learning and the aggregation of local updates from individual devices transmitted to a centralized server. This process should persist until satisfactory performance metrics are achieved.

The SLICES research infrastructure emphasizes the Internet of Things and Internet of Services, as well as cloud, edge, and fog computing, artificial intelligence, and various other domains. (SLICES-SC, 2022) along with distributed systems (SLICES-RI, 2021a) research, which necessitates the implementation of privacy-preserving artificial intelligence techniques to adhere to the directives of the EU General Data Protection Regulation. (GDPR, 2022) directives. This highlights the significance of Federated Learning within the SLICES framework, particularly in a privacy-preserving and heterogeneous setting for instance, in SLICES, data and/or code can be rendered inaccessible to other users of the research infrastructure if desired, such as due to specific policies of an entity or company or other particular requirements..

The inherent diversity of the participating sites, which are federated to create the comprehensive EU-wide SLICES research infrastructure and privacy-preserving facilities, is particularly conducive to the experimentation and validation of Federated Learning methodologies.

The research conducted on the heterogeneity in Federated Learning (FL) has identified several factors that adversely affect the performance of the global model. The computational capacity of the devices involved contributes to a slowdown of the entire system, thereby diminishing global performance. Concurrently, the Non-IID (NIID) data present among the participating clients introduces statistical heterogeneity into the FL framework, which hinders the system’s ability to converge and further deteriorates overall performance.

In FedProx, the inclusion of a proximal term has proven to be a crucial advancement in enhancing the performance of the current model while addressing the challenge of stragglers, especially when compared to other leading architectures. A key advantage of FedProx is its assurance of convergence. There is evidence to suggest that FedAvg serves as an effective algorithm for training data across local devices but it fails to fully interpret the features due to convergence issues. Incorporating an additional proximal term could significantly improve the accuracy of models in numerous existing studies.

3 METHODOLOGY & SIMULATION

This study performed an empirical examination of the FedAvg and FedProx algorithms within various IID and NIID data settings, utilizing the SLICES research infrastructure. Concurrently, it published the analyzed methods in the catalogue for potential use by other researchers.

3.1 Datasets and Models

The simulation is performed on different datasets with their IID and NIID properties. The MNIST with IID and NIID data and CIFAR10 dataset with IID and NIID data are used in the proposed work.

In the scenario of IID data, the MNIST dataset comprises 70,000 samples of handwritten digits, with 60,000 samples designated for training and 10,000 samples allocated for testing. In contrast, with NIID data, the distribution of data varies, as illustrated in Figure 4. In this situation, each client possesses digits that are not aligned with those of other clients, resulting in independent non-identical data. Conversely, the CIFAR10 dataset consists of 60,000 samples, with 50,000 images reserved for training and 10,000 for testing. The images (Dhada et al., 2020) are collected and subjected to preprocessing operations, including segmentation, cropping, and other procedures, prior to being input into the classification model.

In preprocessing the images, the 28x28 MNIST images and 32x32 CIFAR10 images are flattened into matrices. Before that, its dimension is changed to 3D, i.e., 28x28 and one is for the grayscale channel in the case of MNIST, and 32x32 with 3 RGB channels for CIFAR10.

The models are trained using a federated approach, wherein each client maintains its local model that synchronizes with the global model stored in the cloud through model updates. In this work, two models, i.e. deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (Albawi et al., 2017) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) (Taud and Mas, 2018) models, are used for training in different environments with different data distribution and presence of stragglers.

Figure 4: Clients with NIID.

3.2 Simulation Methodology

To analyze the FedAvg & FedProx algorithms, the simulation is performed with 0%, 50% and 90% stragglers and proximal term value $\mu = 0.3$. The simulation consists of 100 participating clients, a 0.1 learning rate and maximum 80 numbers of communication rounds between clients and servers. The following combinations of models and datasets are used in the simulation for 0%, 50% and 90% stragglers and proximal term value $\mu = 0.3$.

1. FedAvg with CNN model on IID & NIID data properties of MNIST and CIFAR10 datasets.
2. FedAvg with MLP model on IID & NIID data properties of MNIST and CIFAR10 dataset.
3. FedProx with CNN model on IID & NIID data properties of MNIST and CIFAR10 dataset.
4. FedProx with MLP model on IID & NIID data properties of MNIST and CIFAR10 dataset.

3.3 Experiments Setup

The simulation is realized on the platform “*SoBigData*”¹ (Giannotti et al. 2018)(Cresci et al., 2019), one of the gateway portals towards the federated SLICES research infrastructure, as well as the namesake of the Italian (country-wide) site of SLICES, by configuring the experiments via a

¹SoBigData e-infrastructure portal: <https://sobigdata.d4science.org>

method published and made available on the infrastructure. The published method executes the simulation as requested, based on the parameters utilized during the experiment’s execution, and yields the desired results. The research infrastructure, to cope with this goal, provides two valuable tools for tests preparation:

1. The *Method Development* page (see Figure 5) is a dedicated environment based on JupyterHub, where through a notebook or console, the developer can write, develop, and interactively test his code in a sandbox provided with useful and ready-to-use libraries;
2. The pair of functions: *Method Importer* and *Method Engine*. Respectively, the former is used to upload and publish a method, and the latter is used to run the experiments according to the simulation parameters.

Figure 5: SoBigData platform: Method Development Launcher.

Following the development phase, the newly implemented method is published (either as a black box or with the code shared) when it is considered valuable, and its dissemination aligns with policies aimed at promoting code reuse across various experiments. The *Method Importer* creates a project for each published method and requires the definition of several components, including input/output, code interpreter, general information, and more. Figure 6 shows a view of the *Comparison_FedAVG_Fedprox* method. Finally, the experiments can be conducted by initiating the method through the appropriate invocation panel (for instance, the function labeled Execute an experiment), and as it is shown in Figure 7, it offers a selection panel to choose the method to be executed based on the available category and description.

Figure 6: SoBigData platform: Method Importer view.

Figure 7: SoBigData platform: Method Invoker view.

4 RESULT & ANALYSIS

In order to evaluate the FL aggregation algorithms, namely FedAvg and FedProx, various scenarios have been simulated by implementing the established methods with appropriate inputs to determine the anticipated behavior of the methods, with the resulting data preserved for subsequent analysis. A careful value assignment to μ is important in the FedProx algorithm. So for the entire simulation, the value of μ is taken as 0.3.

Table 1 shows the accuracy obtained when the probability of stragglers is 0%, meaning there is no straggler in the entire FL setup. When the dataset is MNIST, and the model is a CNN, the accuracy of FedProx is 90.91%, but it is 81.90% in the case of the FedAvg algorithm. So It can be concluded that for NIID data, the FedProx algorithm outperformed the FedAvg algorithm. Furthermore, the performance of the FedProx algorithm is superior in the context of IID data when compared to NIID data, as illustrated in figures 8 and 9.

Figures 10 and 11 represent the comparative performance of FedAvg and FedProx for all the possible combinations of simulations performed

in this work. In the context of any dataset or model, the FedProx algorithm demonstrates superior performance compared to the FedAvg algorithm when dealing with NIID data. Conversely, when only IID data is considered, the performance disparity between the FedAvg and FedProx algorithms is negligible. Therefore, in scenarios where the distribution is IID, the FedAvg algorithm is preferable. However, as the distribution shifts to NIID, the advantages of utilizing the FedProx algorithm become evident. Thus, it can be affirmed that the FedProx algorithm effectively addresses the challenges posed by statistical heterogeneity in federated learning (FL).

Table 1: Performance comparison for FedAvg and FedProx for 100 Clients , 0% stragglers, $\mu=0.3$ and learning rate=0.01.

Dataset	Distribution	Algorithm	Model	Accuracy(%)
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	CNN	93
MNIST	IID	FedProx	CNN	92.66
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	81.90
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	90.91
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	MLP	90.28
MNIST	IID	FedProx	MLP	89.87
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	76.09
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	82.33
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	CNN	83.03
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	CNN	81.75
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	77.28
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	79.17
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	MLP	76.23
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	MLP	75.97
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	69.14
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	73.56

The results obtained with 50% probability for the presence of stragglers, 100 participating clients, and $\mu=0.3$ is shown in Table 2. The accuracy of the FedProx algorithm in the NIID data case is always greater than the FedAvg algorithm. So it can be concluded that the performance of the FedProx algorithm is better in the case of NIID data, as compared to the FedAvg algorithm. It is also observed that with the MNIST dataset, the FedProx works better than FedAvg in the case of IID data but, on the other hand, in the case of the CIFAR10 dataset, FedAvg works better than FedProx in IID data.

Figure 8: Accuracy Graph for FedProx in IID data.

Figure 9: Accuracy Graph for FedProx in NIID data.

The performance of FedProx with MNIST IID distribution is better than CIFAR10 IID distribution which can be seen in Figures 12 and 13. Hence, it can be inferred that in NIID data with 50% stragglers, the performance of FedProx is better than FedAvg. However, in the case of IID data with 50% stragglers, the performance of the FedProx algorithm mostly depends on the type and properties of the dataset being used. Thus, by these results, it can be deduced that FedProx can deal both with system hetero-

Figure 10: Performance Comparison of FedAvg and FedProx with 0% stragglers and $\mu=0.3$ using CIFAR10 dataset.

Figure 11: Performance Comparison of FedAvg and FedProx with 0% stragglers and $\mu=0.3$ using MNIST dataset.

geneity (i.e., characterized by the occurrence of stragglers) and statistical heterogeneity (i.e., dataset distributions and their properties).

Table 3 shows the accuracy obtained when the percentage of occurrence of stragglers is 90%. In this scenario, it has been observed that in both cases, IID and NIID data, the performance of the FedProx algorithm is better than FedAvg. Figures 14 and 15 show the accuracy at different

Table 2: Performance comparison for FedAvg and FedProx for 100 Clients , 50% stragglers, $\mu=0.3$ and learning rate=0.01.

Dataset	Distribution	Algorithm	Model	Accuracy(%)
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	CNN	97.34
MNIST	IID	FedProx	CNN	99.08
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	89.24
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	96.57
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	MLP	91.55
MNIST	IID	FedProx	MLP	92.46
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	85.72
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	94.07
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	CNN	64.09
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	CNN	52.89
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	84.47
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	94.59
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	MLP	55.18
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	MLP	51.48
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	77.28
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	93.30

Figure 12: Performance of FedProx on CIFAR10 IID data with 50% Stragglers.

Figure 13: Performance of FedProx on MNIST IID data with 50% Stragglers.

rounds for the FedAvg and FedProx algorithms with IID data. Similarly, Figures 16 and 17 represent the accuracy of the FedAvg and FedProx algorithms at different rounds with NIID distribution. Looking at these simulation results, it can be deduced that FedProx performs better in intense heterogeneous environments as compared to the FedAvg algorithm.

Figure 14: Performance of FedAvg on MNIST IID data with 90% Stragglers.

Considering all the prior findings, it can be concluded that the FedProx algorithm is consistently favored over the FedAvg algorithm, particularly in scenarios involving both system and statistical heterogeneity.

Table 3: Performance comparison for FedAvg and FedProx for 100 Clients , 90% stragglers, $\mu=0.3$ and learning rate=0.01.

Dataset	Distribution	Algorithm	Model	Accuracy(%)
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	CNN	98.37
MNIST	IID	FedProx	CNN	99.08
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	92.08
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	91.05
MNIST	IID	FedAvg	MLP	82.72
MNIST	IID	FedProx	MLP	93.68
MNIST	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	89.09
MNIST	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	94.19
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	CNN	79.52
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	CNN	87.43
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	CNN	83.12
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	CNN	90.32
CIFAR	IID	FedAvg	MLP	73.39
CIFAR	IID	FedProx	MLP	75.27
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedAvg	MLP	71.42
CIFAR	Non-IID	FedProx	MLP	76.68

Figure 15: Performance of FedProx on MNIST IID data with 90% Stragglers.

Figure 16: Performance of FedAvg on MNIST NIID data with 90% Stragglers.

Within the SLICES research infrastructure, where diverse sites (for instance, those with varying computational and/or storage capabilities) collaborate to form a federation, the advantages of the FedProx algorithm in executing distributed privacy-preserving training without considerable performance loss (such as that caused by the unavoidable occurrence of stragglers) can be clearly emphasized.

Figure 17: Performance of FedProx on MNIST NIID data with 90% Stragglers.

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